

EFFECTS OF LANDSCAPE CHANGE ON BIODIVERSITY IN NIGERIA: REMOTE SENSING AND GIS APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The paper was on the disappearance of natural habitats and the increasing rarity of attractive and beautiful plants and animal species. Some habitats have lost much of their ecological status for the simple reason of man's activities. Most developmental projects such as infrastructure, agricultural and industrial developments have resulted in deforestation. Fire, drought and desertification are inclusive. They cause great impacts on the natural environment with fragmentation and habitat loss. There are changes over a period of time, therefore, Remote Sensing and GIS are considered as veritable tools for the evaluation and monitoring of deforested areas. Conserving biodiversity is to conserve the array of species of plants and animals and other organisms. Estimate of biodiversity in Nigeria shows that there are 22,090 animal, 5081 plant and 1489 species of microorganisms. There is need to guide the use of land in order to minimize and safeguard the destruction and disruption of the natural systems. The paper concluded that there should be periodic ecological audits of sites in order to assess the degree of changes and sustainable use.

KEYWORDS: Developmental projects, Nigeria, RS/GIS

INTRODUCTION

Forests cover 31 percent of the total global land area. These forests give home to 80 percent of Earth's terrestrial biodiversity and the livelihood of 1.6 billion people around the world depends on forests. Recognizing the global importance of forests the United Nations declared 2011 as the International Year of Forests (IYF) to raise awareness on conservation, multiple use and sustainable development of all types of forests.

The main threat to biodiversity is the persisting high rates of deforestation and forest degradation in our forest. A comprehensive, adequate and representative reserve system is a key element in the Nigerian approach to ecologically sustainable forest management practice. The conservation of much of the world's biological diversity depends on the way in which timber production forests are managed. A great percentage of Nigeria's luxuriant vegetation has been removed and several species have become extinct (United Nations 2002). The world Rainforest Movement (1999) records show that between 70 and 80% of Nigeria's original forest has disappeared and presently the area of its territory occupied by forests is reduced to 12%. In the period between 2000 and 2005, Nigeria lost about 2,048,000 ha of forest (FAO 2005). Although Nigerian government established several forest reserves for conservation of forest resources, these forest reserves have been seriously neglected and received little or no improvement in terms of investment and management. In the Second Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Helsinki in 1993, the African countries made a commitment to promote the implementation of the principles of sustainable forest management established at the UN Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio in 1992, both nationally and internationally. This axiom of modern approaches to forest management is encapsulated by the Forest Stewardship Council's Principles and Criteria for Forest Stewardship, which require that forest management maintain intact, enhance or restore biodiversity at all its levels.

Knowledge of biodiversity conservation in managed natural tropical forests has recently been thoroughly reviewed by Putz *et al.* (2000). Pointing out and discussing the fact that the seemingly simple terms "logging" and "biodiversity" both embrace great complexity, they conclude that while timber production forests will not replace protected areas as storehouses of biodiversity, they can and should become a component of an integrated conservation strategy which will potentially cover much greater land areas than are likely to be assigned to strict protection.

For proper conservation, sustainable use and benefit sharing of the Nigerian forest biodiversity, there is need to develop preliminary data on: a) maps of cattle distribution, main crops cultures, mining, population, land use pressure, deforestation, deforestation pattern, fire risk, hydro balance, fires that cut across the whole vegetation in Nigeria. Therefore the assessment of biological diversity becomes increasingly important in the sustainable management and conservation of tropical forests. Some measures to avoid or minimize the threat of significant reduction or loss of biological diversity are necessary for the sustainability of this biological diversity. Forests would be better maintained and protected if forest owners were compensated for the services provided by their forests to society. One of the problems in implementing sustainable management practices is that, although society benefits from it, forest owners usually do not capture these benefits; in this respect, the payment of environmental services is an effective way for internalizing these benefits to those people responsible to implement in the field sustainable practices that contribute to conserve tropical forests. These types of efforts reinforce the multifunctional value of forests, where tropical biodiversity plays a very important role. The underlying hypothesis is that forests would be better maintained and protected if forest owners were compensated for the services provided by their forests to society.

Factors Affecting Loss of Biodiversity

There may be need to conserve large areas because of wide geographical distribution of diversity and complexity of making system involved (National Research Council, 1991) Unstrained and reckless exploitation has led to the depletion of large proportion of the country's vast forest resources.

Population pressure, habitat destruction, over-exploitation, change in land use, pollution and genetic erosion among others constitute the major threat to biodiversity [Ola-Adams 1977 and 1981) Habitat destruction and deforestation have threatened with extinction of 484 plant species in 112 families of 4600 plant species in Nigeria [Okojie, 1999]. Over 350000 hectares of forest and natural vegetation are being lost annually in Nigeria [NEST, 1991].

The conversion of natural landscapes such as forests, grasslands, and wetlands, to agriculture, pastures or settlements is the primary culprit of habitat loss and the endangerment of species. Like land degradation, anthropogenic emission of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxides, puts the region's biodiversity at risk.

In Nigeria, several factors are responsible for loss of biodiversity; deforestation is the main cause, followed by mining. Deforestation is carried out without following the established country's norms. Deforestation may lead to declining water service provision and rising temperatures, having a direct impact on the world's production system. It affects, in particular, protected areas because of a lack of control mechanisms and conflicts between mining and forestry policies/legislation. The direct factors (forest harvesting, mining, poaching, road construction) and indirect factors (socioeconomic crisis, poverty, institutional deficiencies) lead to the loss of Nigeria's forest biological diversity.

Biodiversity Indicators

Indicators can be used to monitor and guide the implementation of the forest policy at all levels. The forest, environmental and biodiversity programmes are implementation programmes, and the realization of the objectives set in these is now measured by commonly accepted indicators.

Biodiversity indicators, as part of the different sets of standards to conceptualize and evaluate Sustainable Forest Management (SFM), have as yet contributed little to sustainable forest management, but may become useful tools to monitor the state of forest ecosystems.

Owing to the changes in the operating environment of forestry, in 1998 it was noted that further development of the criteria and indicators was necessary, and a work group with broad representation from the various interest groups involved in the forest sector (ministries, forest research institutes, universities, and industry and nature conservation organizations) was appointed for this purpose. The task of the work group was to check all the national indicators for sustainable forest management, taking into account the national and international development and the most recent information.

The main objective has been to develop appropriate indicators for measuring the realization of sustainability in forest management and changes in forest ecosystems. A number of distinct indicators have been combined into larger wholes, and certain indicators for compiling basic data have been left out.

Indicators for biological diversity

Indicators relating to the protection and management of biological diversity are divided into three hierarchical levels.

- i. *Regional diversity* covers the abundance and diversity of forest types, communities of organisms and ecosystems, i.e. their number and structural variety.
- ii. *Inter-species diversity* refers to the abundance and diversity of species inhabiting the forests, i.e. variation in the number of species, their relative abundance and functional significance.
- iii. *Intra-species diversity* is the genetic diversity within each species, i.e. the genetic variation of the species. The following indicators for the maintenance and protection of biodiversity in Nigeria can be used:

Indicator 1: Instruments to regulate the maintenance, conservation and appropriate enhancement of biological diversity in forest ecosystems (the descriptive indicator contains data on the following instruments relating to forest management: international agreements and action programmes, Nigeria legislation, conservation programmes and areas and their representativity, economic instruments for protecting forests, monitoring and maintenance of sites of biological diversity in forests, producing information).

Indicator 2: Endangered and vulnerable species (estimated number of endangered species according to habitats based on survey)

Indicator 3: Protected forests and forests with harvesting restrictions (development in the total area of protected forests, ha)

Indicator 4: Valuable forest habitats and their protection (area of valuable habitats according to the National Forest Inventory in the territories of different Forestry Centres, %)

Indicator 5: Tree species composition (dominance of different tree species in the total forest area, %)

Indicator 6: Pure and mixed forest stands (whether the forest composed of one dominant species or a mixture of several species, share of each forest type of the total forest area, %)

Indicator 7: Decayed and wildlife trees in commercial forests and conservation areas (m^3/ha)

Indicator 8: Gene reserve forests (number and area (ha) of these)

Source: FRIN, 2010

The Need for Reserves as a Conservation method

In order to manage and conserve forest resources, Nigeria established several conservation areas. Aminu-Kano and Marguba (2002) reported that Nigeria's first formal (modern) forest reserve was created in 1889. By 1950, forest reserves covered about 8% of the country's land area and gradually rose to 11% by 1980. The forest reserves have for sometime be seriously neglected and have received little or no improvement in terms of investments and management. However, after the UNCED, a number of positive developments have taken place to help the country achieved sustainable forest management. In addition to redelineate and survey of the boundary and updating of maps in a number of forest reserves, inventory has recently (1999) been concluded which provides estimates of wood products supply situation in 28 states of the country (information by the government of Nigeria, 5th session of the UNs convention on sustainable development April 1st 1997).

Forest Conservation Programme in Nigeria

The destruction of natural forest requires the necessity for conservation and various programmes are developed to its effect. For sustainable development quite a number of interest individuals, national and international organizations including FAO, United Nations, UNESCO, International Plant Genetic Resources Institute

[IPGRI], International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources [IUCN] and a host of non-governmental organizations see to the management of ecosystem.

Conservation Methods

The importance of preserving vegetation types was realized as far back as 1946 [Jones, 1948]. Two types of conservation areas have been established by Forest Department in Nigeria [SNR in-violent plots] specifically for protecting of samples of vegetation and plant in perpetuity and game reserves or national parks primarily directed towards the direction of wild animal life. Botanical garden and arboreta have also been established for the propagation and observation of plants for educational and scientific studies.

i In-Situ Conservation

This is feasible where pressure on the natural ecosystem is light and technique of perpetuating ecosystem or species are unknown. Conservation of species in-situ is the best means of conservation of the numerous species, which have recalcitrant seeds [Whitmore, 1999]. Endemic species can also be conserved in-situ, since they are more habitat-dependent. Ola-Adams, [1995], however, observed that this is not possible where the pressure on the natural forest is light. Strict Nature Reserve [SNR], Game Reserve, National Park, Botanical Garden and adequate means of conserving such ecosystem or species.

ii Ex-Situ Conservation

In case where it is not possible to maintain an adequate genetic base for any particular endangered ecosystem or species in areas where it occurs, ex-situ conservation is appropriate.

The Strict Nature Reserve [SNR] include SNR2 [Akure], SNR3 [Urhonigbe], SNR4 [Oban], SNR5 [Ribako], SNR7 [Bonu], SNR8 [Bar Nzelgarma]. There were also gazzetted national parks and game reserves; the Kainji Lake National park, Old Oyo National park, Cross-River National Park, Chad Basin game reserve and Pandam wildlife park. All these reserves were designed to have core areas and buffer zones. Some non-destructive human activities like teaching and research are permissible in the former while hunting, logging, mining, grazing and farming activities are restricted in the latter. The core area was for the conservation of biological resources and the habitats [Ola-Adams, 1996]. There is currently one biosphere in Nigeria, the Omo Biosphere Reserve. SNR is still relatively protected because according to Ojo et al, [1999] not much difference exists in the 1974 and 1998 status of the reserves.

Importance of Conserving Forest

The contributions of forest to human and national development include the following;

1. Education and research: students and researchers acquire more knowledge on how biosphere functions in relation to plants, animals and their habitats study wild plants in conservation areas.
2. Wild plant species are sources of drugs and medicine, which are widely used all over the world.
3. It provides economic products e.g. yeast bread, vegetables, fruits, antibiotics etc.
4. They aid tourism, recreation and national development.
5. They create employment; staff is employed into conservation areas as forest guard and other posts.
6. Forests are sources of fuel, building materials, paper and fibre.
7. They serve as habitats for wildlife and endangered species of plants and animals.
8. Green plants purifies air by removing carbon dioxide during photosynthesis and generating oxygen during respiration
9. Erosion is controlled and provide water resources
10. Forest provide food for man and animals
11. People appreciate the aesthetic nature and value their beauty.
12. Litters from plants decay thereby forming humus and enrich and improve the soil fertility.
13. Strategic use as hide out during war
14. They are used in installing traditional rulers e.g. *Newbouldia laevis*

The contributions of biodiversity resources indicate that its conservation is very essential to human existence and development.

List of Conventions Concerning Conservation of Biodiversity

Various domestic laws and international convention on biodiversity mechanisms have been put in place to conserve country's flora, fauna and marine or fresh water resources in Nigeria. Among such legislations listed by Ola-Adams [1996], and Okorodudu-Fubara, [1998] are:

1. Waterworks Act 1915
2. Wild Animal Preservation Act 1916
3. Oil Pipelines Act 1956
4. Mineral Act 1958
5. Forestry Act 1958
6. Antiquities Act 1958
7. Public Health Act Cap165, 1958
8. Criminal Code, Explosive Act 1964
9. Oil in Navigable Water Act, 1968
10. Petroleum Act, 1969
11. Kainji Lake National Park Decree, 1979
12. Endangered species [Control of International Trade and Traffic] Decree, 1985.
13. Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act, 1985
14. Animal diseases control decree, 1988.
15. Natural Resources Conservation Council Act, 1989
16. Bee [Import Control and Management] Act, 1990
17. National Crop Varieties and Livestock Breed Act, 1990
18. Environmental Impact Assessment Decree, 1992.
19. Bush Burning Edicts of several states; Bush Burning Act, 1986 [Ogun State]', control of Bush Burning Edict, 1989[Ondo State], and Bush Burning Control Edict 1985 [Kaduna State].
20. African conservation on the conservation of nature and natural resources, 1968
21. Convention on African migratory locust, 1962.
22. Convention on the conservation of migratory species of wild animals, 1969
23. Convention of fishing and conservation of the living resources of the high seas, 1958
24. International Convention on Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, 1973.
25. International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution of the sea by oil, 1954
26. Convention conserving the protection of the world cultural and natural heritage
27. Conservation for cooperation in the protection and development of the marine and coastal environment of the west and central Africa region, 1984.
28. Conservation on the prevention of marine pollution by dumping of waste and other matters, 1972.
29. Basel convention on the control of trans-boundary movement of hazardous wastes and their disposal, 1989.

Lack of enforcement, application and implementation of these laws and regulations rendered them useless and ineffective.

Institutional Framework on Biodiversity

For sustainability of these biodiversity, short-term measures address mainly the strengthening of the institutional framework; the protection of ecosystems, vulnerable and endangered species; restoration of degraded areas; and measures for monitoring protected areas. As for long-term measures, emphasis should be put on a better knowledge of forest dynamics, valuation of traditional knowledge and betterment of the life conditions of local communities through institutional reforms.

Specific Measures for Biodiversity Conservation should include:

- (a) Status of forest biodiversity: Assess biodiversity with a view to identifying measures for its preservation, and set aside series of small parcels of land in forestry concessions as protected areas;
- (b) Social context: Assess the impact of the working population in forests. This study should lead to the establishment of a dialogue mechanism bridging enterprises, employees and local populations;
- (c) Operation damages: Evaluate logging and transportation techniques/methods and institute training in reduced impact logging;

- (d) Synergetic interventions: Forest operators should be able to propose, based on inventory, measures aiming to limit impact of activities on animal populations in order to be able to develop appropriate plans/programmes for fauna management;
- (e) Protected species: Update the Red List of threatened or endangered species and ecosystems;
- (f) Protected areas: Increase the surface of protected areas up to 4 million hectares, as planned in legal texts already in force, and reinforce their protection;
- (g) Forest management: Development and implementation of management plans in forest concessions;
- (h) International conventions: Development of consolidated strategies and action plans for the Implementation of international convention signed and ratified by Nigeria, in particular CITES and the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Strategies to Support, Improve and Sustainably Manage Species Composition (Flora and Fauna)

- i. Identify, delineate and inventories species and sites of conservation interest
- ii. Develop in-situ conservation areas as national parks, game reserves, strict nature reserves, sanctuaries and cultural heritage centres
- iii. Develop ex-situ conservation areas – zoological and botanical gardens, which are to serve as centres for genetic improvement of endangered species
- iv. Promote herbarium/arboretum establishment – support the establishment and development as both national and state priority
- v. Develop transparent mechanisms for responsibility and benefit sharing among federal, states and local governments and communities and other stakeholders
- vi. Enforce forestry legislation including laws on export of flora and fauna
- vii. Initiate the development and dissemination of relevant awareness and education materials on biodiversity conservation.

Source: National Forestry Policy, 2006

As biodiversity became popularized in the late 1980's, many scientists agreed that more information was needed for quick determination of conservation priorities in disappearing rainforest ecosystems. Murray Gell-Mann proposed rapid assessment to study poorly understood forests in the tropics (Wolf 1991). Rapid assessment (RAP) teams were deployed to regions that are threatened with imminent loss of biodiversity. This approach involves visiting the region by a team of taxonomic experts, who quickly gather collections and site information. RAP teams identify areas that merit highest protection priority. Their findings are applied immediately and directly to conservation and land-use planning through close work with local colleagues.

Government Intervention

Quick response from Nigerian government to take an urgent steps in the;

- (i) Assessment of regional conservation priorities on a subregional and bioregional basis.
- (ii) Broad assessment of landscape/ecosystem/species priorities for conservation.
- (iii) Identification of the range of conservation measures required to conserve biodiversity in each subregion/bioregion in terms of reserve consolidation, off-park conservation and integrated Natural Resources Management strategies.
- (iv) Identifying the range of actions required and the associated resource implications to conserve biodiversity across a range of environments.
- (v) Extrapolation of case studies across similar subregions to identify broad management and resource implications.
- (vi) Development of a distributed database in each jurisdiction on biodiversity and management needs at the regional scale.

National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan

To protect and conserve the remaining biodiversity of the forest ecosystem, adopted the strategies and actions of the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) sets forth. The six strategies identified are:

1. Expanding and improving knowledge on the characteristics, uses and values of biological diversity.
2. Enhancing and integrating existing and planned biodiversity conservation efforts with emphasis on in-situ activities.
3. Formulating an integrated policy and legislative framework for the conservation, sustainable use, and equitable sharing of the benefits of biological diversity.

4. Strengthening capacities for integrating and institutionalizing biodiversity conservation and management.
5. Mobilizing an integrated Information Education and Communication (IEC) system for biodiversity conservation.
6. Advocating stronger international cooperation on biodiversity conservation and management.

Suggestions on the need of Biodiversity Conservation

In order to increase the capacity of ecological protection, including efficient conservation, of forest biodiversity, it is required to:

- improve the legal background, institutional framework and management of forest resources;
- ensure the functional connection between fragmented forest compartments;
- extend the area of afforested lands up to 15% of the national territory;
- facilitate the natural regeneration of the forest stands having a balanced diversity, structure and functions;
- conserve rare and endangered taxa and communities;
- monitor the forest biodiversity components etc.

More efforts should be directed towards reinforcing the role that Sustainable Forest Management could play to contribute to the conservation of tropical forests and its biodiversity. This role has to be seen along with other efforts to establish and properly manage protected areas and tree plantations. Policy aiming at improving the techniques to reduce the impact of forest operations in natural forests, while at the same time increasing the benefits to forest owners and local communities. Short-, mid- and long-term measures which could stop the present trend of biodiversity loss and allow for the restoration of the forest cover up to a level that could at the same time meet human needs as well as economic and environmental requirements of the goods and services of forest biodiversity should be adopted.

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